

On the presence of *Zelus renardii* Kolenati, 1857 (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Reduviidae) in Germany

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ABSTRACT: The presence of *Zelus renardii* Kolenati, 1857 in Germany is discussed. The first record of a nymph of the species in Germany is reported.

KEY WORDS: *Zelus renardii*, alien species, first records, distribution, Germany.

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The first record of the Nearctic assassin Heyden (2021), based on a single adult bug species *Zelus renardii* Kolenati, 1857 specimen which was found in October (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Reduviidae: 2020 in the city of Teningen, located in Harpactorinae: Harpactorini) for Baden-Württemberg in southwest Germany was reported by van der Germany.

Very likely, the specimen had been imported with grapes from Italy which were bought in a supermarket (van der Heyden, 2021).

Now, another record of *Z. renardii* from Germany can be reported: On 08.10.2023, Laura Bounin photographed a nymph of the species (Fig. 1) in the city of Karlsruhe, also located in Baden-Württemberg.

Interestingly, the nymph was found on a balcony outside a building on a pepper

plant (*Capsicum* sp.). The plant was not bought, but has been growing there from seed since May 2023. No imported plants, fruits or vegetables were bought and stored nearby (Laura Bounin, pers. comm.). Thus, it is very likely that the nymph was not introduced with goods from Southern Europe, but hatched from egg in the wild.

Recently, the first record of *Z. renardii* from Austria, an adult specimen found in April 2023 on a broccoli bought from a nearby organic farm, was reported from the city of Graz (van der Heyden & Staudinger, 2023).

The specimens from Graz and from Karlsruhe were found more or less at the same latitude: 47.126269 and 49.005428, respectively.

Obviously, *Z. renardii* is currently expanding its European distribution northwards from the Mediterranean Region, crossing the Alps.

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Figure 1. Nymph of *Zelus renardii* Kolenati, 1857, Karlsruhe, Germany, 08.10.2023. (Photo: Laura Bounin).